

An invariant for networks generated by Collatz-type algorithms

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14.10.2025

Abstract. For an extended class of Collatz-type algorithms, a “network divisibility” invariant was found using a constructive-topological approach. Its main property is that the divisibility of the entire network is decomposed into a product of the divisibilities of its constituent parts raised to powers equal to the natural densities of the network's constituent parts. The invariant is directly related to the convergence of algorithms.

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1. Introduction

This article continues the approach to the Collatz conjecture proposed previously [1, 2]. In the first article, the problem was conceptualized as a task of the structure of the network generated by Collatz-type algorithms. The second article proposes using geometric mean properties of network structures to study the structure of the corresponding networks. This article refines the definition and reveals the essence of the “network divisibility” invariant discovered in this approach.

For the sake of consistency between the articles, we will adhere to the definitions and designations already used earlier. The definition of the Collatz algorithm for positive integers is standard: $3n+1$ if n is odd and $n/2$ if n is even. For the original algorithm, we use the mnemonic notation “ $3n+1/2$ ” (a reminder of the order of operations) or shorter “ $3n+1$ ”. The class of Collatz-type algorithms includes algorithms of the general form “ $an+b/c$ ” (a similar mnemonic notation), where a and c are positive relatively prime numbers, and b is an integer. The Table with keys and pointers (see Fig. 1) refers to a table of expansions of natural numbers in powers of 2 with “keys” (the column of all odd numbers n) and “pointers” (even numbers of the form $3n+1$ in rows). Similarly, tables of expansion of all numbers in powers of any base $c = 3, 4, 5...$ are constructed.

The Table with keys and pointers helps to topologically represent and explore the network defined by the algorithm. In the case $3n+1$, the network topology is a rooted tree. The root is the key to which the algorithm converges. A cycle is a set of several keys, a cyclic variant of the root. In the general case of algorithms of the form $an+b/c$, the network may consist of several “rooted trees” and a “rootless subnet.” The reason we insist on our own terminology (network, keys, pointers) is that it is more adequate for the object under study.

1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512
3	6	12	24	48	96	192	384	768	1536
5	10	20	40	80	160	320	640	1280	2560
7	14	28	56	112	224	448	896	1792	3584
9	18	36	72	144	288	576	1152	2304	4608
11	22	44	88	176	352	704	1408	2816	5632
13	26	52	104	208	416	832	1664	3328	6656
15	30	60	120	240	480	960	1920	3840	7680
17	34	68	136	272	544	1088	2176	4352	8704
19	38	76	152	304	608	1216	2432	4864	9728
21	42	84	168	336	672	1344	2688	5376	10752
23	46	92	184	368	736	1472	2944	5888	11776
25	50	100	200	400	800	1600	3200	6400	12800
27	54	108	216	432	864	1728	3456	6912	13824
29	58	116	232	464	928	1856	3712	7424	14848
31	62	124	248	496	992	1984	3968	7936	15872
33	66	132	264	528	1056	2112	4224	8448	16896
35	70	140	280	560	1120	2240	4480	8960	17920
37	74	148	296	592	1184	2368	4736	9472	18944
39	78	156	312	624	1248	2496	4992	9984	19968
41	82	164	328	656	1312	2624	5248	10496	20992

Fig. 1

2. Network divisibility

Article [2] introduced an important property — “the divisibility Δ averaged over the entire network, calculated as the geometric mean of the divisors 2^p over all even pointers of the network.” Let us define Δ more thoroughly.

A well-known analogue is the average divisibility by 2^p over the entire series of even natural numbers 2, 4, 6, 8..., which is simply calculated through the sum of the series $2^{(1+1/2+1/4+1/8+\dots)} = 2^2 = 4$. We prefer to calculate it using the geometric mean over a series of divisors $2^1, 2^2, 2^1, 2^3\dots$, which gives the same result in the limit. For the simplest algorithm $1n+1/2$, if the pointers of its Table are arranged in ascending order, we obtain the same series of all even numbers and the same limit divisibility $\Delta = 4$. It is logical to extend this definition to all algorithms of the form $an+b/2$. A specific algorithm has its own pointer placement scheme and its own order of divisors. But, as numerical verification on different algorithms has shown, in all cases, the divisibility of the entire network tends to 4 in the limit. A typical change in Δ with an increase in the number of pointers taken into account is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2

Such a definition of network divisibility Δ can naturally be extended to the entire class of Collatz-type algorithms of the form $an+b/c$. This gives rise to a general

formula for network divisibility $\Delta(c) = c^{c/(c-1)}$, which is easily derived by summing the corresponding series, similar to the case $c = 2$. A selective numerical check for algorithms with base $c = 3, 4, 5$ confirms the tendency to converge to the correct value. A formal proof of this statement is routine and of no interest.

Definition of network divisibility for Collatz-type algorithms: network divisibility $\Delta(c) = c^{c/(c-1)}$ is the limit value of the geometric mean over a series of divisors c^p extracted from the pointer scheme of any algorithm of the form $an+b/c$ after sorting the pointers in ascending order.

The dependence of Δ only on the parameter c allows us to call network divisibility an invariant for a subset of algorithms with the same base. But this characteristic has another, even more significant property.

Let's take an arbitrary Collatz-type algorithm and write down the geometric mean over a partial series of divisors e_i from its pointer scheme:

$$D_k = (e_1 e_2 e_3 \dots e_k)^{1/k}, \text{ where } k \text{ is the number of terms in the series.}$$

Let us imagine that the network corresponding to this algorithm consists of two parts, for example, a rooted tree and a rootless subnet. Any key and any pointer belongs either to the rooted tree or to the rootless subnet. We group the pointers according to their belonging, count them separately, and start manipulating their divisors f_i, g_i :

$$D_k = (f_1 f_2 f_3 \dots f_m \times g_1 g_2 g_3 \dots g_n)^{1/k}, \text{ where } m+n = k,$$

$$D_k = ((f_1 f_2 f_3 \dots f_m)^{m/m} \times (g_1 g_2 g_3 \dots g_n)^{n/n})^{1/k},$$

$$D_k = (f_1 f_2 f_3 \dots f_m)^{m/mk} \times (g_1 g_2 g_3 \dots g_n)^{n/nk},$$

$$D_k = ((f_1 f_2 f_3 \dots f_m)^{1/m})^{m/k} \times ((g_1 g_2 g_3 \dots g_n)^{1/n})^{n/k},$$

$$D_k = (D_m)^{m/k} \times (D_n)^{n/k}, \text{ where } D_m \text{ and } D_n \text{ are the geometric means of the parts.}$$

Passing to the limit $k \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain the main formula of the invariant:

$$\Delta(c) = (\Delta_{\text{root}})^{\omega_{\text{root}}} \times (\Delta_{\text{unroot}})^{\omega_{\text{unroot}}} = c^{c/(c-1)},$$

where $\omega_{\text{root}} + \omega_{\text{unroot}} = 1$ is the sum of the limiting shares of all network pointers (which is equivalent to the limiting shares of keys) belonging to the rooted tree and the rootless subnet, respectively. 2 equations with 4 unknowns.

Thus, the divisibility of the entire network $\Delta(c)$ is decomposed into the product of the divisibilities of the rooted tree Δ_{root} and the rootless subnet Δ_{unroot} , raised to powers equal to the natural densities of the network's constituent parts. This conclusion easily generalizes to networks of any composition. This is an invariant for networks generated by Collatz-type algorithms.

First considerations in connection with the found invariant. Under the assumption of the coexistence of a rooted tree and an rootless subnet, the inequality $\Delta_{\text{unroot}} < \Delta(c) < \Delta_{\text{root}}$ is obviously true. In addition, the inequality $c < \Delta_{\text{unroot}} < a^+$ is always true, where the lower bound is related to minimal divisibility, and the upper bound is caused by the nature of the rootless subnet [2]. Finding an upper bound for Δ_{root} is difficult. The well-known result of Tao [3] corresponds to the limit $\omega_{\text{root}} \rightarrow 1, \Delta_{\text{root}} \rightarrow 4$ when $c = 2$.

Based on the invariant, a first prediction can be made. A complete rootless network (its condition $\omega_{\text{unroot}} = 1, \Delta_{\text{unroot}} = \Delta(c)$) cannot exist when $a < \Delta(c)$, and corresponding algorithms of the form $an+b/c$ must have at least one root. This can be verified on previously unexplored algorithms with base $c = 3$ or more.

3. Conclusion

The discovery of the invariant confirms the productivity of the constructive-topological approach to the $3n+1$ problem and similar algorithms. It also provides additional evidence in favor of the network conceptualization of the task. It turns out that not only numerical sequences are connected in network structures, but also topologically separate rooted trees and rootless subnets are not autonomous, since they share a common limited resource of network divisibility.

References

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